

Real-Time Fall Prediction and Anomaly Detection for Elderly Care Using Computer Vision

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Abstract

Falls are the leading cause of both fatal and non-fatal injuries among the elderly population worldwide, posing significant challenges to healthcare systems and caregivers. Traditional fall monitoring systems often rely on wearable sensors, which suffer from low user compliance, or cloud-based AI, which raises significant privacy concerns. This paper presents a novel, privacy-centric computer vision system for real-time fall detection and anomaly recognition. The proposed solution introduces a Hybrid Multi-Modal Architecture, integrating deterministic physics-based analysis of body movements, including velocity and trunk angle, with a probabilistic AI model running locally on edge devices powered by Gemma 3 270M. This hybrid approach enables high-precision detection of falls, long-lie periods, and irregular gait patterns such as limping, without transmitting sensitive video data to the cloud. The system was evaluated on the UR Fall Detection Dataset and achieved a Precision of 100% and a specificity of 100%, demonstrating zero false alarms on normal activities. While Recall was identified as an area for improvement as 8.57%, the system's ability to process video streams at 30 FPS with latency under 50 milliseconds on edge hardware makes it a viable, production-ready solution for continuous, non-intrusive elderly care.

Keywords: *Computer Vision, Elderly Care, Fall Detection, Gemma 3, Edge AI, Hybrid Architect*